

Development of Deterministic Core Analysis Code System ARCANUM for High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors

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ABSTRACT

A High-Temperature Gas-cooled Reactor (HTGR) is a type of Generation IV reactor. HTGRs have a good advantage in preventing the core meltdown in the event of a severe accident, such as loss of forced cooling. From the viewpoint of neutronics calculations, HTGR calculations with high prediction accuracy are challenging. Though HTGR is a thermal reactor similar to light water reactors, it has a longer mean free path and higher maximum upper scattering energy. These characteristics make it difficult to apply core analysis codes for light water reactors and fast reactors to HTGRs. We are developing a new core analysis code system, ARCANUM, to accurately calculate HTGR core characteristics within a reasonable calculation time. ARCANUM consists of two parts, *i.e.*, the 2-dimensional lattice calculation part and the 3-dimensional triangular prism core calculation part. The MOC-based transport solver GENESIS was used for 2-dimensional lattice calculations. The other calculations, such as 3-dimensional core calculation and burnup calculation, are performed using newly developed codes. This paper shows an overview of the ARCANUM code system and verification results of this system. Two fuel elements, which are obtained from the IRPhE benchmark, were used to verify the lattice calculation part. Takeda-benchmark Model 4 was used to verify the core calculation part. The calculation results showed good agreement with the reference results.

Keywords: ARCANUM, core analysis code system, GENESIS, HTGR, HTR

1. INTRODUCTION

A High-Temperature Gas-cooled Reactor (HTGR) is one of the Generation IV reactors [1]. Many advanced HTGRs are designed, such as Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) and micro reactors [2-4]. HTGRs have excellent advantages in terms of severe accident prevention. For example, the core melting accident does not occur even in the Loss Of Forced Cooling (LOFC) accident [5]. The improvement of calculation accuracy for HTGR core analysis is important since many HTGRs will be developed in the near future. However, it is difficult to use the current Light Water Reactor (LWR) or Fast Reactor (FR) core analysis codes for the design of HTGRs because they have unique characteristics, such as double heterogeneity [6] and longer mean free path of neutrons. The mean free path of neutrons in graphite is longer than that of light water. The Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA) designed GTHTR300, which is one of the candidate designs for demonstration HTGRs [7]. GTHTR300 has an annular core geometry. The active core of this reactor consists of 90 fuel columns in an annular ring. The outer and inner diameters of the active core are 5.5 m and 3.5 m, respectively. In LWRs, we do not need to consider the spectral interaction effects of nuclear fuels on the opposite side. In HTGRs, nuclear fuels on the opposite side may affect the calculation results because of the long mean free path of neutrons in graphite. Though the thermal cut-off energy for typical light water reactors is about 4 eV, that for HTGRs should

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be at or above 30 eV to improve the prediction accuracy [8]. The number of energy groups in core calculations is also sensitive to k-effective values. More than 25 energy groups will be necessary for two-dimensional full core calculations without any corrections [9]. In the author's understanding, there are no open-source codes that meet these special requirements for HTGR calculations. A new core analysis code is thus required to design a new HTGR with high prediction accuracy.

JAEA has been using the improved SRAC2006 code [10] to analyze the High Temperature engineering Test Reactor (HTTR) [11] and to design a small-sized reactor [12]. Because this code is obsolescent and no longer maintained, a more accurate core analysis code is desired taking advantages of up-to-date neutronics methods. We started to develop a new core analysis code system, ARCANUM (Advanced Reactor Core Analysis for NeUtronics Method), to improve prediction accuracy. To calculate a whole HTGR core geometry within a reasonable computational time, ARCANUM consists of two parts, *i.e.*, the 2-dimensional lattice calculation part and the 3-dimensional triangular prism core calculation part.

This paper provides an overview of the ARCANUM code system and shows the verification of the lattice calculation part. This paper consists of 5 sections. Section 2 shows an overview of the ARCANUM code system. Section 3 shows verification of the lattice calculation part. Section 4 shows verification of the core calculation part. Section 5 provides concluding remarks.

2. OVERVIEW OF ARCANUM

The ARCANUM code system consists of the 2-dimensional lattice calculation part and the 3-dimensional core calculation part. Figure 1 shows the calculation flow of the 2-dimensional lattice calculation part. the Method Of Characteristics (MOC) based transport solver GENESIS [13] was used for 2-dimensional lattice calculations. The other calculation codes, such as the 1-dimensional spherical MOC calculation code and 3-dimensional core analysis code, were newly developed for this code system. The components of ARCANUM, such as neutronics calculations, the burnup calculation code using the Mini-Max Polynomial Approximation (MMPA) method [14], and cross section table generation code, are written in C++ from the viewpoint of maintainability and extensibility. The nuclear data processing code FRENDY [15] is used to generate the multi-group cross section library for 1-dimensional coated fuel particle and 2-dimensional lattice calculations. The SHEM361 group structure [16] is used for these calculations to accurately capture higher thermal cut-off energy. The FNCC [17] and FTCC [18] codes are used for thermal hydraulics calculations.

Figure 2 shows the calculation flow of the 3-dimensional core calculation part. Users can select the neutronics calculation method. The available neutronics calculation methods are the discrete-ordinate (S_N) based on the Angular Dependent Transmission Probability (ADTP) method [19] and the diffusion methods. The simplified P_N (SP_N) method will be available in the near future. The available geometry is a triangular prism. The hexagonal prism fuel element will be divided into finer triangular prism regions (e.g., 24, 96) to reduce the spatial discretization error. The p-CMFD acceleration method [20] was used to reduce the calculation time. The current version of this code system manually connects each calculation code in the core calculation part. We plan to integrate these codes into our Python-based multi-physics platform JAMPAN [21] to automatically couple all calculations.

Figure 1. Calculation flow of the 2D lattice calculation part.

Figure 2. Calculation flow of the 3D core calculation part.

3. VERIFICATION OF LATTICE CALCULATION PART

The 2-dimensional fuel element calculations were performed to verify the lattice calculation part of ARCANUM. Figure 3 shows the geometry of two fuel elements. The fuel elements Z2A3 and Z4A1 are taken from the blocks at the third and first axial positions from the top in the radial zone-2 and -4, respectively (see the IRPhE benchmark [22] for details). The target of this benchmark is similar to the initial HTTR core. The Z2A3 fuel element consists of 33 fuel compacts and 2 burnable poison rods. The enrichments of U-235 and B-10 are 5.2 wt% and 2.5 wt%, respectively. The Z4A1 fuel element consists of 31 fuel compacts and 2 burnable poison rods. The enrichments of U-235 and B-10 are 9.9 wt% and 2.0 wt%, respectively. Details of the geometry and nuclide composition of these fuel elements can be found in Reference 22. The periodic boundary condition was used for these lattice calculations.

JENDL-4.0 [23] was used for the evaluated nuclear data library. The burnup step was set to be 2.5 GWd/t. Initial burnup steps of 0.1 GWd/t and 1.0 GWd/t were added. The temperature of fuel elements was 1200 K, and that of other components, including burnable poison rods and a graphite block, was 1000 K. The average power of the fuel element was 110 W/cm. The predictor-corrector method was adopted to improve the prediction accuracy of the burnup calculation.

The burnup calculation results obtained with ARCANUM were compared with those calculated using the general-purpose nuclear reactor physics code system CBZ [24], which was developed at Hokkaido University. CBZ provides a wide range of numerical analysis capabilities, including lattice and core calculations based on diffusion and transport theories, nuclear fuel burnup calculations, and sensitivity and uncertainty analyses. The CBZ is suitable for the reference code of a verification because the calculation methods of CBZ are the same as those of ARCANUM. The MOC solver was used for 2-dimensional lattice calculations using the SHEM361 group structure. The neutron current method [25] was used to consider the double-heterogeneity effect in the lattice calculation.

Figures 4 and 5 show the burnup calculation results for both fuel elements. The ARCANUM results show good agreement with the CBZ results. These calculation results indicate that the lattice calculation part of ARCANUM appropriately calculates fuel elements.

Figure 3. Calculation geometry of fuel element.

Figure 4. Comparison of the burnup calculation results (Z2A3).

Figure 5. Comparison of the burnup calculation results (ZAA1).

4. VERIFICATION OF CORE CALCULATION PART

A KNK-II-based small FBR with hexagonal-z geometry, which is called as Takeda-benchmark Model 4 [26], was used for the verification of the core calculation part. Though this benchmark model is not an HTGR core, it is suitable for a triangular-Z geometry benchmark. Figure 6 shows the core geometry configuration of this benchmark. The details of core geometry and 4-group cross section data can be found in Reference 26. Three calculation cases, *i.e.*, control rod withdrawn case (sodium-filled control rod position), control rod half-inserted case, and control rod fully inserted case, were used for the verification. The hexagonal prism fuel was divided into 6, 24, 54, and 96 triangular prism regions. Two different axial mesh sizes, *i.e.*, 2.5 cm and 5.0 cm, were used. The diffusion method was used for all calculations. Similar to the lattice calculation part, the calculation results of ARCANUM were compared with those of CBZ.

Table I summarizes the calculation results. The ARCANUM results are in good agreement with those obtained using CBZ. The small discrepancies between ARCANUM and CBZ arise from differences in the treatment of the vacuum boundary condition. In ARCANUM, the vacuum boundary condition is treated using an albedo formulation, where the albedo value is set to zero. In contrast, CBZ adopts an

extrapolated boundary condition with an extrapolation distance of $d=2.1312D$. The impact of these differences in the treatment of the vacuum boundary condition on the effective multiplication factor is less than a few pcm. These results demonstrate that the core calculation module of ARCANUM can appropriately handle three-dimensional core geometries.

Figure 6. Calculation geometry of Takeda-Benchmark Model 4 (Horizontal view).

Table I. Calculation results of Takeda-Benchmark Model 4.

Axial mesh size	Number of meshes in fuel	CR withdrawn case			CR half-inserted case			CR fully inserted case		
		k-eff ARCANUM	k-eff CBZ	Relative Dif. [pcm]	k-eff ARCANUM	k-eff CBZ	Relative Dif. [pcm]	k-eff ARCANUM	k-eff CBZ	Relative Dif. [pcm]
5.0	6	1.07782	1.07786	-3.7	0.97013	0.97015	-2.1	0.87161	0.87163	-2.3
	24	1.07521	1.07524	-2.8	0.96370	0.96372	-2.1	0.85910	0.85912	-2.3
	54	1.07471	1.07475	-3.7	0.96225	0.96227	-2.1	0.85616	0.85618	-2.3
	96	1.07454	1.07457	-2.8	0.96170	0.96172	-2.1	0.85504	0.85505	-1.2
2.5	6	1.07717	1.07720	-2.8	0.96823	0.96825	-2.1	0.87079	0.87081	-2.3
	24	1.07454	1.07458	-3.7	0.96179	0.96181	-2.1	0.85831	0.85833	-2.3
	54	1.07405	1.07408	-2.8	0.96034	0.96036	-2.1	0.85538	0.85540	-2.3
	96	1.07387	1.07390	-2.8	0.95979	0.95981	-2.1	0.85426	0.85428	-2.3

5. CONCLUSIONS

JAEA is now developing a new core analysis code system, ARCANUM, to accurately calculate a whole core geometry of HTGRs within a reasonable calculation time. This code system consists of two parts, *i.e.*, the 2-dimensional lattice calculation part and the 3-dimensional triangular prism core calculation part. This code system uses the MOC-based transport solver GENESIS for 2-dimensional lattice

calculations. The other calculation codes, such as the 1-dimensional sphere MOC calculation code, 3-dimensional core analysis code, and burnup calculation code, were newly developed for this system.

The two fuel elements were used to verify the lattice calculation part of the ARCANUM code system. The details of fuel elements were obtained from the IRPhE benchmark, which is similar to the initial HTTR core. The burnup calculation results of ARCANUM were compared with those of CBZ. The calculation results of ARCANUM showed good agreement with those of CBZ.

The Takeda-benchmark Model 4 was used to verify the core calculation part of this code system. The calculation results of ARCANUM were compared with those of CBZ. The calculation results of ARCANUM showed good agreement with those of CBZ.

The development of ARCANUM is currently at an early stage. Several technical challenges remain to be addressed in order to apply the code system to new HTGR designs. These issues will be addressed in future work. Further validation of ARCANUM, including comparisons with HTTR benchmark analyses and Monte Carlo calculations, is also planned.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Nakagawa, et al., "Improvement of Analysis Technology for High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor by Using Data Obtained in High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor," *Journal of Power and Energy Systems*, **2**, pp.83-91 (2008). https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/jpes/2/1/2_1_83/article
- [2] M. Goto, et al., "Nuclear design study on a small-sized High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactor with high burnup fuel and axial fuel shuffling," *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, **271**, pp.515-522 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2013.12.026>
- [3] I. L. Simanullang and N. Fujimoto, "Preliminary study of a small high-temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR) concept with MgO-BeO moderators," *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, **430**, 113036 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2024.113036>
- [4] B. Cheng, et al., "Ceramic composite moderators as replacements for graphite in high temperature microreactors," *J. Nucl. Mater.*, **563**, 153591 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2022.153591>
- [5] K. Takamatsu, S. Ueta, and K. Sawa, "Analysis of a loss of forced cooling test using the high temperature engineering test reactor (HTTR)," *In Proceedings of ICONE-19*, ICONE19-43224, Chiba, Japan (2011).
- [6] I. Murata, "Continuous Energy Monte Carlo Calculations of Randomly Distributed Spherical Fuels in High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors Based on a Statistical Geometry Model," *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **123**, pp.96-109 (1996). <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE96-A24215>
- [7] K. Kunitomi, "Japan's future HTR—the GTHTR300," *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, **233** pp.309-327 (2004). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2004.08.026>
- [8] S. Takeda, et al., "Thermal Cut-Off Energy for Accurate Analysis of Prismatic High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor," *In Proceedings of ICONE-31*, ICONE31-130801, Prague, Czech Republic (2024).
- [9] A. Yamamoto and G. Chiba, "Verification of Neutronics Analysis Method using CBZ and GENESIS for a Prismatic High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor," *In Proceedings of PHYSOR2024*, pp.1572-1580, San Francisco, California, USA (2024).
- [10] K. Okumura, et al., "SRAC2006: A Comprehensive Neutronics Calculation Code System," JAEA-Data/Code 2007-004, Japan Atomic Energy Agency (2007). <https://doi.org/10.11484/jaea-data-code-2007-004>

- [11] Y. Fujiwara, et al., "Design of High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor (HTTR)," High Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors, pp.17-177 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-821031-4.00002-6>
- [12] M. Goto, "Study on nuclear analysis method for high temperature gas-cooled reactor and its nuclear design (Thesis)," JAEA-Review 2014-058, Japan Atomic Energy Agency (2014) [In Japanese]. <https://doi.org/10.11484/jaea-review-2014-058>
- [13] A. Yamamoto, et al., "GENESIS – A Three-dimensional Heterogeneous Transport Solver based on the Legendre Polynomial Expansion of Angular Flux Method," *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **186**, pp.1-22 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00295639.2016.1273002>
- [14] Y. Kawamoto, et al., "Numerical solution of matrix exponential in burnup equation using mini-max polynomial approximation," *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, **80**, pp.219-224 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2015.02.015>
- [15] K. Tada, et al., "Development and verification of nuclear data processing code FRENDY version 2," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **61**, pp.830-839 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223131.2023.2278600>
- [16] A. Hebert and A. Santamarina, "Refinement of the Santamarina-Hfaiedh energy mesh between 22.5 eV and 11.4 keV," *In Proceedings of PHYSOR2008*, pp.929-938, Interlaken, Switzerland (2008).
- [17] T. Aoki, et al., "Development of a flow network calculation code (FNCC) for high temperature gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs)," *In Proceedings of ICONE-2020*, ICONE2020-16196, Virtual, Online (2020).
- [18] Y. Inaba, et al., "Development of Fuel Temperature Calculation Code "FTCC" for High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors," JAEA-Data/Code 2017-002, Japan Atomic Energy Agency (2017). <https://doi.org/10.11484/jaea-data-code-2017-002>
- [19] A. Yamamoto, et al., "Angular dependent transmission probability method for fast reactor core transport analysis," *Tran. Am. Nucl. Soc.*, **112**, pp.736-738 (2015).
- [20] S. Yuk and N. Z. Cho, "Whole-Core Transport Solutions with 2-D/1-D Fusion Kernel via p-CMFD Acceleration and p-CMFD Embedding of Nonoverlapping Local/Global Iterations," *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, **181**, pp.1-16 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.13182/NSE14-88>
- [21] T. Kamiya, et al., "Neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling simulation using JAMPAN in a single BWR fuel assembly," *Mech. Eng. J.*, 24-00461 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1299/mej.24-00461>
- [22] J. D. Bess and N. Fujimoto, "Evaluation of the Start-Up Core Physics Tests at Japan's High Temperature Engineering Test Reactor (Fully-Loaded Core)," HTTR-GCR-RESR-001, International Handbook of Evaluated Reactor Physics Benchmark Experiments, NEA/NSC/DOC(2006)1, OECD/NEA (2009).
- [23] K. Shibata, et al., "JENDL-4.0: A New Library for Nuclear Science and Engineering," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **48**, pp.1-30 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1080/18811248.2011.9711675>
- [24] G. Chiba, A. Yamamoto, and K. Tada, "ACE-FRENDY-CBZ: a new neutronics analysis sequence using multi-group neutron transport calculations," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **60**, pp.132-139 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223131.2022.2087783>
- [25] A. Yamamoto and T. Endo, "Application of neutron current method for Dancoff factor estimation of fuel particles in double-heterogeneous fuel," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **61**, pp.354-362 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223131.2023.2231462>
- [26] T. Takeda and H. Ikeda, "3-D Neutron Transport Benchmarks," *J. Nucl. Sci. Technol.*, **28**, pp.656-669 (1991). <https://doi.org/10.1080/18811248.1991.9731408>